

GUIDE FOR THE COMBINED APPLICATION OF THE FUNCTIONAL RESONANCE ANALYSIS METHOD AND INTERDEPENDENCE ANALYSIS

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Scope

The document describes step-by-step guidelines to use Interdependence Analysis as an extension of the traditional FRAM method, a novel combination of two existing safety analysis methods. Even if the aim of the development was on a framework for Human-Robot Interaction, the Interdependency assessment explained in this document can be applied to any multi-agent system with task and goal coordination. The examples in this instruction guide are not applied to robot applications, but to an aviation example in which both human and technical agents are engaged to achieve a mission or task.

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Introduction

This document provides guidelines to use the principles from Interdependency Analysis (IA), a formative tool for human-machine team requirements, as an extension to the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM), the latter being a method to model the performance of socio-technical systems. IA characterises goal coordination capabilities between human-machine teams engaged in joint activity, by describing the functional interaction between the socio-technical agents in terms of essential interdependence relation types (Johnson et al., 2018b).

IA was originally developed as part of co-active design to describe the increasingly sophisticated interaction between people and robots. This guide will focus on human-machine goal coordination in line with IA's original intent, although it could theoretically be applied to human-human goal coordination

Note that IA is not part of a traditional FRAM analysis.

The guide is structured as follows:

- Section 1 contains **blue text** for the original FRAM methodology, quoted from: 'A Brief Guide on how to use the FRAM' (Hollnagel, 2018). The interested reader can find an even more comprehensive explanation of FRAM theory in (Hollnagel, 2012).
- Section 2 adds novel 'black text' to describe how the traditional FRAM method can be extended with Interdependency Analysis (IA). Experienced FRAM users, already familiar with the traditional method, can therefore focus on the black text only.
- Appendix A is created to support the reader in maintaining oversight of the different aspects of the framework, describing the methodologic elements required by both the traditional FRAM methodology, and the IA extension. It is recommended to regularly consult the appendix workflow while reading the different sections of this guide.
- Appendix B represents a Resilience Analysis Matrix (RAM) representation of a generic FRAM model. The use of RAM is optional, but can be supportive for a systematic analysis of FRAM models with many functions.

It is recommended to download and install the FRAM Model Visualizer (FMV), the application that was used to build the FRAM models in this FRAM-IA guidelines. The FMV is in the public domain, hence free of charge. The download link can be found here: <https://zerprize.co.nz/home/FRAM>. The FMV does not support features that are explained in this guide in the IA section, which was manually added by superimposing them on the traditional FRAM model.

A first version of this guide has been updated by processing the feedback of FRAM experts (n=8). The experts were assigned to two groups and independently tried to apply the FRAM-IA guidelines to a FRAM model which was specifically prepared for a workshop. The reader is

invited to also send feedback for future updates of this document as a practical manual to apply the recently developed FRAM-IA framework

1. Traditional FRAM

The purpose of the FRAM is to analyse how something has been done, how something is done, or how something could be done to produce a representation of it in a reliable and systematic manner, using a well-defined format. This resulting representation is effectively a model of the activity because it captures the essential features of how something is done. In the case of the FRAM, the essential features are the functions that are necessary and sufficient to account for the activity together with the way in which the functions are coupled or mutually dependent.

The FRAM proposes that everyday events and activities can be described in terms of the functions involved without predefining specific relations, levels, or structures. (. . .) The FRAM thus does not have an embedded model, not even a non-linear one, and makes no assumptions about how the system under investigation is structured or organised, nor about possible causes and cause-effect relations. It describes the functions using six aspects. (. . .) The FRAM can be described as a method that is used to produce a model, instead of a method that is derived from a model and can therefore be seen as representing a method-sine-model approach.

As an alternative to linear causality and cause-effect reasoning, the FRAM proposes that the variability of two or more functions can coincide and either dampen or amplify each other. The variability of one function may in this way come to affect the variability of other functions in analogy with the phenomenon of resonance.

2. How to build a traditional FRAM model

The Functional Resonance Analysis Method consists of four stages:

- Stage #1 - Identify and describe the important system functions and characterise each function using six basic characteristics (called aspects). Together, the functions constitute a FRAM model.
- Stage #2 - Characterise the potential variability of the functions in the FRAM model, as well as the possible actual variability in one or more instantiations (or realisations) of the model.
- Stage #3 - Determine the possibility of functional resonance based on dependencies/couplings among functions given their potential / actual variability.

- Stages #4 - Develop recommendations on how to monitor and manage the variability, either by attenuating variability that can lead to undesirable results, or by enhancing variability that can lead to desired results.

The FRAM brief guide from Hollnagel (2018) mainly focuses on the first and the second step and covers some elements of step 3. In this document, additional guidelines are presented to extend the FRAM with IA principles, which will add an extra framework dimension to characterise the possibility of functional resonance in terms of the goal coordination potential between human and technical agents. The extension of FRAM with IA supports stages #3 and #4 in the process.

2.1. FRAM Stage #1: Identifying and Describing Functions

2.1.1. What is a Function?

In the FRAM, a function represents the means that are necessary to achieve a certain goal. More generally, function represents the acts or activities – simple or composite – that are needed to produce a certain result. Unlike tasks, functions can be carried out in different ways and by different means.

A function typically describes what people – on their own or together – have to do to perform a specific task and thus achieve a specific goal. (. . .) A function can also refer to something that an organisation does. (. . .) A function can finally refer to what a technical system does.

A FRAM function is thus more than a task as the term is commonly used. A function describes what needs to be done, but not necessarily how or by what means

2.1.2. Describing Functions (guided by a scenario of making cup noodles)

A general rule for the use of the FRAM is that a function should be described by a verb if it is a single word, or a verb phrase – in both cases using the infinitive form. For instance “(to) diagnose a patient” rather than “diagnosing a patient” or “(to) start a pump” rather than “starting a pump” or “pumping water”.

At this point, you should begin to use the FMV. Depending on how many functions you defined, the outcome may look something like Figure 1. In this example, six functions have been defined. At this stage of development, they are not connected or coupled, and their position on the FMV canvas is not significant. At the moment they are only identified by their name, which is a verb phrase as recommended. It may be useful even for this simple example also to write something in the Description field, for instance, who or what carries out the function.

Figure 1: Six functions in the preparation of cup noodles (Hollnagel, 2018).

2.1.3. FRAM Aspects

The FRAM characterises functions by means of six aspects named Input, Output, Precondition, Resources, Control, and Time, respectively. The general rule of the FRAM is that an aspect of a function should be described when it is seen as necessary or appropriate by the analysis team, provided there is sufficient information or experience to do so. It is thus not necessary to describe all six aspects of every function, and it can indeed sometimes be either impossible or unreasonable to do so.

A general rule in the use of the FRAM is that an aspect is described using a noun, or a noun phrase. In other words, an aspect is described as a state or as a result of something – but not as an activity.

Figure 2: The six aspects used to characterise functions Aspects (Hollnagel, 2018).

The different types of aspects can be interpreted from Figure 2. More details about the description of aspects can be found in (Hollnagel, 2018, 2012).

2.1.4. Couplings

Every function in a FRAM model is characterised by using some or all of the six aspects. If the same values (names) are defined for aspects of different functions – for instance, the Output of one function and the Time of another – then there is a potential coupling between the functions. This is shown by the FMV as a line that connects the two aspects.

Figure 3: Six functions and their couplings in the preparation of cup noodles (Hollnagel, 2018)

Note: The labels from functions in FRAM are typically notated between <> signs, i.e. <function label>, whereas the couplings are typically placed between squared brackets [], i.e. [coupling label].

The couplings in a FRAM model are generally n-to-n (or many-to-many) rather than 1-to-1. For example, the function <To read instructions> has two different Outputs which serve as Control for three other functions. The same Output, [Filling guidance], is defined as a Control aspect of both <To pour boiling water until fill mark> and <To close and weigh down lid>. The couplings that in this way are described in a FRAM model, i.e., the dependencies that are the consequence of shared aspect attributes, are called potential couplings. This is because a FRAM model describes the potential or possible relationships or dependencies between functions without referring to any particular situation. In an instantiation of a FRAM model, only a subset of the potential couplings can be realised; these represent the actual couplings or dependencies that have occurred or are expected to occur in a particular situation or a particular scenario. An instantiation of a FRAM model thus represents how a subset of functions can become mutually coupled under given conditions or within a given time frame. The couplings realised for a specific instantiation do not vary but assumed to be are 'fixed' or 'frozen' as long as the conditions exist.

2.1.5. Foreground and Background Functions

In Figure 5, there are four foreground functions and five background functions. Foreground functions are white while background functions are shaded grey. The determination of whether a function is a foreground or a background function is made automatically by the FMV using the following rules:

- A function that only has an Output – or Outputs – defined, is designated a background function.
- A function that only has an Input – or Inputs – defined is designated a background function.
- All other functions are designated foreground functions.

Because background functions are assumed not to be variable while the activity being analysed takes place, there is no need to expand them further by describing their Preconditions, Controls, etc. A background function can thus be seen as being part of the boundary of the system being analysed. Background functions typically represent something that is used by foreground functions, but which is assumed to be stable during the situation under consideration.

2.1.6. Upstream and Downstream Functions

While the terms foreground and background represent a function's role in a model, the terms upstream and downstream are used to describe the temporal relationship between a function that currently is in focus and the other functions. The analysis of the FRAM model takes place by tracing the potential couplings as they lead from function to function. This means that there will always be one or more functions that are in focus, i.e., whose variability is currently being

considered. The functions that have been in focus before, which means functions that already have been carried out, are referred to as upstream functions. Similarly, the functions that follow the function (or functions) that are in focus, are called downstream functions. During an analysis, any function can change status from being downstream, to come into focus, and to become an upstream function.

2.1.7. Scale Invariance Property of Traditional FRAM

Scale invariance refers to the fact that the processes that give rise to phenomena on a small or a large scale can be described in the same way (Hollnagel, 2018). The property of scale invariance assures that a taxonomy is not needed to describe higher level phenomena and the functional analysis and the resonance between the functions can be applied to all levels. However, the level of describing the functions depends on the scope of analysis. Be mindful that for the purpose of Interdependence Analysis, typically a higher granularity is needed than encountered in most existing FRAM analyses, because the scope of the analysis is essentially on the couplings between human and technical agents.

At the end of this Section 2.1 the first three elements of the FRAM-IA framework are provided, at this point consisting of the sub-elements needed to simply build a FRAM model that together constitute the first step in FRAM, identification and description of functions. Appendix A at the end of this guide shows how these three steps required when making any FRAM model are also part of the remainder of the FRAM-IA framework.

Figure 4: Steps 1-3 (out of a total of 10) from the FRAM-IA Framework.

2.2. FRAM Stage #2: Characterising the Variability of Functions

A FRAM model can be used to understand how the variability and adjustments can affect other functions and thereby the activity as a whole. Functions can mutually dampen each other (absorb variability) so that the situation can become stabilised. Functions can also mutually reinforce each other (amplify variability) so that the situation becomes unstable and leads to unexpected and usually also unwanted results. The description of the potential couplings can be used to understand emergent outcomes and also how such developments can be monitored and managed.

2.2.1. Variability

The potential variability describes what might happen under different conditions. The actual variability describes what should reasonably be expected to happen under given conditions

(existing assumptions about demands, opportunities, and resources), i.e., for an instantiation of the model.

The graphical rendering of a FRAM model produced by the FMV does, of course, show the lines [couplings] between the aspects of the functions. But the lines should be seen as representing potential rather than actual couplings or connections. Upstream functions may affect downstream functions but not in the usual sense of cause-effect relations. An Input to a function, therefore, does not “cause” the Output. An Input can start a function, but how the function is carried out, hence what the Output will be, may depend on the other aspects (downstream-upstream couplings) as well as the endogenous (a result of the variability of the function itself) and exogenous variability (due to the variability of the work environment).

A FRAM model can be used for several types of analysis, retrospective as well as prospective (. . .). The FRAM model is not intended to be a model of the accident scenario but rather a model of the activity when it goes well. By understanding how it goes well, by identifying how the functions are coupled, and by describing the characteristic or typical variability of the functions, it becomes possible to understand why the outcome in the specific case differed from the many other cases where everything went well. Or consider a case where the FRAM is used to represent a future scenario, for instance, a new proposal for a guideline or procedure. In this case the FRAM model can be used to look for potentially critical upstream-downstream couplings.

2.2.2. The Manifestations of Variability (phenotypes)

Note that the FRAM allows a simple description of variability which only describes two characteristics and a detailed description which describes more options.

The simple description characterises the variability of a function’s Output in terms of time and precision. In terms of time, an Output can occur too early, on time, too late, or not at all. (The last category, ‘not at all’, can be seen as an extreme version of ‘too late’. In terms of precision, an Output can be precise, acceptable, or imprecise. (More detailed characterisations can of course also be used.) Because the Output provides the coupling between upstream and downstream functions, the meaning of precision is relative rather than absolute. An Output can be described as precise if it meets the needs of a downstream function.

The detailed description of Output variability can be with respect to time (too early, too late) and duration (short, long), strength (weak to strong), distance (too long, too short) and direction (wrong direction), object or target (wrong item, wrong recipient), and finally with regard to sequence or order (of two or more sub-activities).

2.2.3. Potential and Actual Variability

The potential variability describes what might happen under different conditions. The actual variability describes what should reasonably be expected to happen under given conditions

(existing assumptions about demands, opportunities, and resources), i.e., for an instantiation of the model.

3. Extending FRAM with Interdependency Analysis

This section introduces the extension of the traditional FRAM with Interdependence Analysis (IA). The case study in 3.1 will be used as a practical example to introduce the further IA steps in the FRAM-IA model.

3.1. Case Study Scenario Introduction

As an example, we will take a typical aviation scenario, supported by Figure B, in which the figure elements have been labelled by the three fundamental principles used in Interdependence Analysis (Johnson et al., 2014), being Observability, Predictability, and Directability (OPD). These principles will be explained in more detail in Section 3.5. Figure 4 introduces a take-off scenario, where the changes in the aircraft's aerodynamic control are interpreted by the pilots via the semantical information of the cockpit instruments during take-off, typically with the autopilot engaged. In terms of observability, the artificial horizon shows the aircraft's attitude and the airspeed indicator (Fig 5.a). Additionally, the angle between aircraft attitude and airstream can be read on the angle of attack indicator, which is also an indication of how close the aircraft is to a stall (loss of aerodynamic lift). An imminent stall would be guided by a stick shaker (a device providing haptic vibrations to the pilots' flight control to produce a warning). Although the stick shaker contains an element of predictability related to anticipating the aerodynamic (system) boundaries, IA theory specifically assigns warnings as a directability principle (Johnson et al., 2018a, 2014), because warnings are meant to immediately direct or redirect behaviour of an agent (See section 3.5 for more details). Concerning predictability the pilot also notices the difference between actual and stall speed (Fig 5, element 5.b). In addition, the small magenta bar shown as an additional column above the airspeed indicator displays a trend indication of the aircraft's speed (Fig 5, element 5.c), showing the projected speed within 6 seconds under equal conditions. This again supports system boundary prediction (predictability). If anything goes wrong with the sensors (e.g. mechanical failure of the static-pitot tube for speed indication or angle of attack vanes for the aircraft's aerodynamic angle), or if any of the instruments would show false readings, the pilot has the possibility to disconnect the autopilot (directability). This is achieved by pushing a disengage button under the pilot's thumb at the yoke (flight control) to resume manual flight. Notice that both aircraft and tasks are designed in such a way that any issues in observability and predictability will not lead to a system failure (a crash) because of the possibility of directability, in this case being the option to regain manual control flying based on essential instrument inputs, while ignoring ambiguous instrument readings (e.g. maintain an aircraft attitude by keeping an attitude range on the artificial horizon that has been learnt during pilot training to perform a safe escape manoeuvre).

Figure 5: aircraft take-off/climb attitude, airspeed indication with stall speed indication and trend indication and autopilot disconnect possibility (adapted from Kashman et al., 2000; Upset Recovery Industry Team, 2008, as cited in: Le Vie, 2014).

See Figure 6 for a FRAM model concerning the physical propagation of representations across media in a typical aviation take off scenario providing a functional representation of the elements in Figure 5.

Figure 6 –FRAM model of functions involved in monitoring and controlling an aircraft during take-off/climb

The model represents how the sensors feed the aircraft instruments inputs, which produce semantical information displayed to the pilots. This can be interpreted by the pilots subsequently controlling the flight controls. The same sensors also provide the inputs for the autopilot. The crew can disengage the autopilot and resume manual control if there is a risk that the autopilot might receive false inputs from sensors.

3.2. Assigning Function Granularity

Note that the functions which were described in Figures 1 and 3 in the cup noodle scenario (from Section 2), taken from ‘A Brief Guide on how to use the FRAM’ (2018), were all performed by human agents, whereas the FRAM also provides the possibility to have technical and organisational agents. In other words, technical agents and even artefacts can also produce functions (verbs), in line with the description of a function in FRAM theory that “the Output can represent material, energy, or information (Hollnagel, 2018). Note that in the cup noodle example the interaction with non-human agents is implied, in the couplings, but not made explicit in the form of functions performed by technical agents. A good example is |tender noodles| as the outcome from the function <to wait until tender> performed by a human agent. With a higher granularity functional description the coupling |tender noodles| could also be produced from

the perspective of the noodles acting as an agent of its own, this time as the output from a function <produce physical reaction to boiling water>. Although such a model with technical agent granularity is normally not required for the scope of preparing cup noodles with highly stable and predictable physical reactions, it is needed when applying IA analysis because IA typically aims to capture exchanges between users and system states or technical agents. This increased granularity is meaningful for complex socio-technical systems where informational and materialized states and representations are transformed, combined, and propagated through the system to enable goal coordination between multiple agents. Remember that the principle of the scale invariance, introduced in Section 2.1.7, makes it possible to describe the phenomena including the technical functions as agents in the same way. For an in-depth discussion on the scale invariance of FRAM, and its levels of resolution to be used during a FRAM analysis, the interested reader can find additional information in (Patriarca et al., 2017)

Transformation of task-relevant information into its subsequent state from a functional perspective allows a systematic analysis of socio-technical systems while circumnavigating the problem that researchers and safety analysts have no access to the internal representations that underlie human cognition or sense-making (Adriaensen et al., 2019). Such internal representations are consequently ill-suited for being accurately described by a functional analysis. Instead, this guide proposes to examine, as previously described by Hutchins (1995) “the role of the material media in which representations are embodied, and in the physical processes that propagate representations across media. Making a functional model with these guidelines reveals how systems that are larger than an individual may have properties in their own right that cannot be reduced to the cognitive or functional properties of individual persons or agents. This is in line with previous work from Hutchins (Hutchins, 1995) and the theory of Joint Cognitive Systems (Hollnagel and Woods, 2005)

In the process of modelling and function description, it can be helpful to think about what constitutes the transformation of task-relevant information as something which requires a change in human perception of the information or signal flow or causes changes in physical appearances.. Identifying granularity is not described by any fixed set of rules in the FRAM, other than choosing the functions in line with the scope and problem space of the analysis. However, the minimum level of granularity for a FRAM-IA analysis can be obtained by following these rules of thumb:

- Describe any transformation of information across media (e.g. physical-semantic transformation, visual-aural transformation) as a new function in the model.
- Describe the different ‘physical’ changes from task-relevant processes that propagate through the system as functions (e.g. physical-physical transformation, liquid-gas).
- Describe any *inter-agent* exchange in the task-relevant transformation of information as a new function. Deliberate inspection of *inter-agent* exchanges supports the process of systematically completing the model.
- Describe the automation mode changes or system configuration changes as distinct functions in the FRAM model. The Inputs will be the aspects that are needed to trigger

mode changes or configuration changes, while the Outputs are the effects or propagation possibilities produced. Automation mode and configuration changes typically alter the predictability and directability (see Section 3.4 below) of system behaviour.

- Psychological processes, computational, and autonomous systems should, as much as possible, be described by the observable system outcomes they produce and not by internal cognitive or computational black box processes. Researchers or safety analysts do typically not have access to things like psychological processes or software coding in terms of tangible or salient signals. However, the scope of the analysis remains the leading principle. Note that contrarily, modelling the work perspective of a psychology researcher or software developer for example, would produce models where such salient cues are produced by the nature of their scope and access to other types of tangible data (e.g. brain firing imaging from EMR brain scans, data transfers from log files, electrical signals from hardware systems, etc.). From the analysis perspective of a clinical psychologist researcher or software developer such information is not black box information anymore. Hence, taking the perspective of the observer has an influence on the scope of analysis.

3.3. Assigning Agent Granularity

In order to correctly allocate the function granularity, it can help to also think about the agent granularity. Allocating functions and agents will typically be an iterative process, but it is recommended to first decide which agents you think interact with the system under analysis. It is recommended to abandon the traditional boundary between medium and agent from traditional safety analysis methods in favour of also accepting technical systems, media, and physical artefacts as agents. This is labelled as the principle of agent-neutrality.

An important reason for agent-neutrality is that regarding the analysis of joint activity, IA requires that the model should be able to represent all viable team role alternatives of the solution space, not of a specific solution related to a single scenario or event. IA calls this the agent-agnostic (another name for agent-neutral) modelling of joint work. This refers to the fact that the description of the work should not be restricted by optimal team compositions or (human or technical) individual team agent capabilities (Johnson et al., 2018b), other than these that are actually observed. This is compatible with the fact that the FRAM is intended to describe the potential relationships or dependencies between functions as a whole without referring to any particular situation (Hollnagel, 2018). Describing particular situations or configurations is possible, but in FRAM this is called an instantiation (see Section 2.1.4). A FRAM model represents normal work as a whole and is more than an instantiation. It logically follows that the choice of agent granularity has an influence on the function granularity produced by these agent as described above in Section 3.2.

Systems are composed of subsystems which are in turn composed of components. The agent granularity at which transformation of information occurs is typically the granularity of

3.4. Assessing Dependency Requirements: Dependency and Capacity to Support/Assist

To define interdependency, one first must recognize that interdependencies are often not mutual dependencies but emerge from an agent needing the support of another to complete its task or fulfil its responsibility. There is a fundamental relation between capacity and dependency, whereby “capacity is the total set of inherent things (e.g., knowledge, skills, abilities, and resources) that an entity requires to competently perform an activity individually” and “dependence exists when an entity lacks a required capacity to competently perform an activity in a given context” (Johnson et al., 2014, p. 47).

Interdependence can be defined as “the set of relationships used to manage dependencies” (Johnson et al., 2014, p. 49). These dependencies can be either strictly *required* or *opportunistic*. Required interdependence originates from a lack of capacity, in which one agent ‘requires’ a complementary agent to fulfil its role or task. This FRAM-IA framework will label this as a *hard dependency* (See Table 1). . Many aspects of teamwork are not about hard dependencies, but about what agents do to facilitate team performance in terms of redundant reminders, auxiliary warnings, providing redundant information and monitoring, etc. The absence of such opportunistic interdependencies which this framework will henceforth call soft dependencies, will not strictly make the system fail. Having soft dependencies provides redundancy and resilience to the system, especially under reduced operational system margins. (See Table 1).

Table 1 - dependency table, adapted from (Johnson et al., 2014, 2018b), but tailored to FRAM's upstream and downstream agents¹

Upstream agent	Downstream agent	Dependency	Requirement Met/Failed
Agent needs assistance	Agent can provide (sufficient) assistance	Hard	Met
Agent can provide (sufficient) assistance	Agent needs assistance	Hard*	Met
Agent cannot assist	Agent cannot assist	Hard*	Failed
Agent needs assistance	Agent cannot assist	Hard	Failed
Agent cannot assist	Agent needs assistance	Hard*	Failed
Agent can do it without assistance	Agent cannot assist	Soft*	Brittleness
Agent cannot assist	Agent can do it without assistance	Soft*	Brittleness
Agent can provide (sufficient) assistance	Agent can provide (sufficient) assistance	Soft*	Resilience
Agent needs assistance	Agent can provide assistance but not without affecting performance, efficiency, or reliability	Hard	Failed/met (depends)
Agent can provide assistance but not without affecting performance, efficiency, or reliability	Agent needs assistance	Hard*	Failed/met (depends)
Same agent for upstream and downstream function		No dependency	No dependency

*Dependencies indicated with an asterisk are the ones to expect in most situations.

Due to the nature of how FRAM reflects reality, it logically follows that in most cases the upstream function (producing an output) is the one that provides the assistance and the downstream

¹ One significant change to the original IA table from Johnson (2014, 2018b) is that the perspective of having a performing and supporting agent was changed into upstream and downstream agent, in line with FRAM modelling.

function (receiving an Input, Precondition, Resource, Time, Control) is the one being dependent on that assistance. Because FRAM is often applied to analyze socio-technical systems, hence inter-agent exchanges performing co-agency, FRAM models describing systems that work as intended will show predominantly green-orange dependency pairs, and rarely orange-green dependency pairs. Exceptions exist and an example is provided in a later section.

Note that the dependencies from Table 1 provide a basis for later steps of assessing performance variability (See Step 3.9). The colour coding at the very right of Table 1, provides a colour code for the requirement description (i.e., the resulting dependency pair as the combination of column 1 and 2):

- red means the propagation ends (broken link², i.e. a broken coupling) in the coupling under investigation
- light green means the propagation continues with desirable positive functional resonance
- dark green not only means desirable positive functional resonance, but additionally indicates resilience.
- yellow means the propagation continues with suboptimal endogenous variability, a result of variability of the function itself.

Note that these requirement descriptions from column 4 are not further graphically displayed in the Figures from the following sections below. Only colour codes of columns 1 and 2 are provided in subsequent figures.

3.5. Assessing Goal Coordination Capability Types (OPD)

The dependency types from Table 1 can further be labelled by the principles of Observability, Predictability and Directability (OPD) as the three central organising principles for goal coordination (Johnson et al., 2014, 2018b) between multiple agents. The OPD principles of IA correspond to the following definitions:

- *“Observability means making pertinent aspects of one’s status, as well as one’s knowledge of the team, task, and environment observable to others.”* (Johnson et al., 2018b)
- *“Predictability means one’s actions should be predictable enough that others can reasonably rely on them when considering their own actions.”* (Johnson et al., 2018b)
- *“Directability means one’s ability to influence the behaviour of others and complementarily be influenced by others.”* (Johnson et al., 2018b)

² Note that a broken link is accounted for as a negative variability because in the specific case of goal coordination it prevents the mission performance from being accomplished.

Typical examples of forms of OPD principles for goal coordination in actual systems can be found in Table 2. IA typically looks at subsystems and agents that are autonomous or semi-autonomous (e.g. robots, self-driving cars), but this guide extends the table to non-autonomous systems like interfaces, instrumentation, and when necessary even artifacts, in line with the theory of Joint Cognitive System. Table 2 – Interpretation of OPD Principles, adapted and extended from (Johnson et al., 2014) – the list is not exhaustive.

OPD principles	Description	Can take the following forms
Observability	<p>AUTONOMOUS AGENTS: transmitting and receiving status, knowledge of the team, task, and environment</p> <p>NON-AUTONOMOUS AGENTS: transmitting current information, signals, states</p>	reveal status
		reveal intention
		interpretation of signals
		transformation of information across media
		transmission of physical states and forces
		inputs to monitoring actions
Predictability	<p>AUTONOMOUS AGENTS: the degree to which others can rely on outcomes when considering their own actions</p> <p>NON-AUTONOMOUS AGENTS: the degree to which a system predicts future system states or reveals future system status</p>	a priori agreements
		the use of models
		synchronization of actions
		use of time-projected information
		cues that support the prediction of boundary conditions for users
Directability	<p>AUTONOMOUS AGENTS: the ability to direct behaviour and to have one's behaviour directed</p> <p>NON-AUTONOMOUS AGENTS: the ability to direct physical control and system states</p>	task allocation
		role assignment
		guidance
		suggestions
		warnings
		control transfer
		corrective actions (incl. outputs of monitoring actions)

The OPD labels are assigned to the couplings between two functions (See Figure 7) in the form of a black label that carries the first letter (O, P, or D) to designate if the coupling is specified by Observability, Predictability, or Directability. Note that due

Just as is the case with differentiating between potential and actual variability in the traditional FRAM (see Section 1), the dependency relationships from Table 1 can be coupled to their actual or potential variability. Potential dependency usually describes how the dependency is intended or designed (Work-as-Imagined/Work-as-Designed), the actual dependency in terms of its phenotype(s) describes what should reasonably be expected to happen under given conditions (existing assumptions about demands, opportunities, and resources). The latter described an instantiation of the model (Work-as-Done). The model from Figure 7 is uniformly standardised over a wide range of aircraft and over many decades. Consequently, this model can be considered to represent the potential and actual dependencies of a single model.

Note that for the interdependence analysis, we are only interested in inter-agent exchanges. Functions and their couplings performed by the same agent do not produce an inter-dependency, as there is no lack of capacity in need for a supporting agent. In terms of interdependence, one can therefore only label aspects that cross the dashed boxed lines, indicating an inter-agent exchange (See Figure 8).

Figure 8 – Take-off/climb scenario with agents' dependency colour coding and OPD labels.

Note that Figure 8 only produces one coupling that does not result in an *inter*-agent exchange, connecting the two functions performed by the pilot agent (far right of Figure 8). Such an *intra*-agent exchange is indicated by the two white boxes (no interdependence) up and downstream of the coupling [abnormal instrument parameters]. Consequently, no OPD labels are assigned. As these two functions depict the cognitive decision that leads to the pilot's reaction to interpret a potential abnormal instrument, this constitutes a cognitive process. We only have access in terms of the action produced by the pilot, and as an analyst or researchers, we cannot directly assess the cognitive mechanisms in functional terms. It is therefore consistent with the focus of our analysis on merely labelling inter-agent exchanges. Now, this does not mean that the coupling [abnormal instrument parameters] does not play a role in the functional propagation and the performance variability of the model as a whole. The coupling can therefore receive a phenotype indicating good or poor manifestation of the variability (e.g. phenotype too late or imprecise). Such an intra-agent exchange (white-white pair) will still positively or negatively affect the inter-agent couplings downstream of that function as in traditional FRAM and resonate with other functions. It can just not receive a dependency, or OPD label because there is only one agent involved.

3.6. Functional Clustering – Grouping Functions into Joint Cognitive Agents

Note that the functions from Figure 7 were still grey, but have meanwhile been assigned the colours green, blue, and red in Figure 8. Be mindful that these colours do not correspond to using the FMV colouring option to indicate the agent that performs the function, as previously applied in several other FRAM publications. The guide uses dashed lines instead around group functions to indicate agents to achieve this. In this guide, the option to colour functions in the FMV concerning the IA extension is used instead to cluster functions by the functional purpose of the joint activity, independent from the agents involved. It is therefore named a Joint Cognitive Systems (JCS) agent. The term JCS agent is used to indicate that different agents work together on a single functional purpose in co-agent relationships.

Which JCS agents are assigned, depends on the scope of the analysis. In our aviation scenario the colours assign the following JCS agents (See Figure 8):

- green: aerodynamic behaviour
- blue: system status support
- red: flight control

JCS agents can later be used for the assessment of joint activity characteristics.

3.7. Actual vs. Potential Variability for Coordination Capability Types (OPD)

So far, we have looked at the 'potential' variability of the model, which led to exclusively having green-orange dependency pairs in Figure 8, and which can be expected from a well-functioning aircraft system design perspective with several decades of demonstrated performance. The meaning of the green-orange colour pairs is that the downstream agent is strictly dependent on

the upstream agent to provide its Output (previously defined in Table 1) and additionally informs that the upstream agent can provide the necessary assistance to complete the activity.

Let us deliberately introduce an instantiated failure that negatively affects performance, in this case, indicated by a yellow-orange dependency pair. This can be illustrated by applying the aforementioned coordination of goals between pilots and aircraft systems to the well-known B737 MAX crashes (see AIB, 2020; KNKT, 2019), in which there was a malfunction of the [angle of attack vane position] (See Figure 9). While Figure 8 produces a model of the potential variability of the joint activity in the majority of aircraft designs, Figure 9 produces a model of the actual variability of the joint activity in the B737 MAX designs before the fleet was grounded in 2019. The instantiation includes an angle of attack malfunction with negative downstream propagation, i.e. there still is an instrument indication, but the physical position of the angle of attack vane is not representative of the aerodynamic angle of attack of the aircraft.

Figure 9 – Take-off/climb scenario adapted to the B737 MAX crashes (2018 and 2019 - simplified)

Note that this is an oversimplification of what happened during the B737 MAX crashes, but the basic mechanisms of sensors, instruments, and the possibility to resume manual control (or the lack thereof) remain valid. In the accident instantiation (observed variability derived from the

accident reports), the actual performance phenotype of the [angle of attack vane position] is negatively affected, indicated by the yellow-coloured boxes from the dependencies.

The failure of an aircraft sensor is rare, but also not unique (Le Vie, 2014), and has equally happened on non-B737 MAX aircraft. Complete system failure, however, was produced in resonance with the fact that the pilots were not able to fully resume the manual control when the augmented automation of the aircraft overruled the pilots' inputs. This anomaly was specific to the B737 MAX design. The FRAM model will not deal with this as a failed dependency but as a conflict of propagation, which is the subject of Section 3.8. At this point, it is important to remember that the potential to alter the directability of the aircraft was constrained by design (see B737 MAX accident reports AIB, 2020; KNKT, 2019)³ and this is not yet uncovered with the techniques presented in this guide so far.

Figure 8 produced a model from which the performance is in line with standardized aircraft design and the majority of flights (work-as-designed and routine operation). Contrarily, Figure 9 shows an instantiation where the performance phenotypes have failed the requirements of goal coordination in a specific instantiation (altered B737 design and failed Angle of Attack sensor). In the instantiation, the sensors provided erratic inputs and ultimately there was no possibility for the pilots to resume manual control because of functional resonance.

Finally, Figure 10 provides a summary of steps of the FRAM-IA framework in addition to the traditional FRAM.

³ The fact that the autopilot relied on a single angle of attack sensor instead of a comparison of two single angle of attack sensors is another co-agency issue specific to the B737 MAX design, which is not included in the simplified model from Figure 8.

Figure 10: Steps 4-8 (out of a total of 10) from the FRAM-IA Framework.

4. FRAM Stages #3 and #4: Determining Functional Resonance and Managing Performance Variability

There is no fixed set of rules in the FRAM to aggregate and manage functional resonance. Instead the FRAM theory refers to the fact that aggregating and managing functional resonance ultimately depends on the nature of the system under observation. Future research will be needed to understand how functional resonance can be managed in the particular challenges and contexts of different work systems. However, the FRAM-IA framework can support generic rules to aggregate and manage functional resonance. Mechanisms for downstream propagation of performance variability propagation in terms of interdependency pairs. Table 3 is based

Table 3 – legend for colour coding previously used in the last column of Table 1 (last column represents the outcome on coupling level (i.e. the outcome for the dependency pair between (resulting from up-and downstream colour coding)

outcome from inter-dependency	colour coding	described effect on coupling outcome	aggregation effects on functional resonance (in terms of downstream propagation)	manage functional resonance
Failed		Red means the propagation ends (broken link ⁴), i.e. a broken coupling) in the coupling under investigation	Downstream functions are negatively affected because of the broken link effect. Downstream functions logically will not be activated if the function under consideration is the only coupling leading to subsequent function(s)	Investigate effects on socio-technical model: (i) Either mitigate the broken coupling, or (ii) use alternative coupling routes to restore the problem (see step 10 in Figure 11)
Met		Light green means the propagation continues with desirable/positive functional resonance	Downstream functions and propagation are not affected	No action needed
Resilience		Dark green not only means that propagation shows desirable positive functional resonance, but additionally indicates a potential for system resilience because both agents are able to	This situation can typically create redundant, or multiple functional routes. Essentially it indicates a potential for positive resonance amplification, but potential for	Verify functional conflict potential possibly created further downstream in the model

⁴ Note that a broken link is accounted for as a negative variability because in the specific case of goal coordination it prevents the mission performance from being accomplished.

		positively support performance. This shows a potential for amplification of positive resonance	negative conflicts further downstream in the model need to be verified because two agents act simultaneously on a single task	
Brittleness		Grey means that one agent is capable of performing a function on its own, and the other agent from the other function is not able to assist. Strictly speaking this coupling does not involve assistance in terms of co-agency, but neither does it negatively affect system performance. Its outcome is neutral on an interdependence level	Neutral propagation, because co-agency is not generated at this point of the model	No action needed
Suboptimal		Yellow means that the request for providing assistance is met, but the propagation continues; although with suboptimal performance variability in terms of performance, efficiency or reliability	Downstream functions are affected. Negative functional propagation effects (negative phenotypes for accuracy, performance or timing issues) for the coupling under investigation will be propagated downstream	Verify effects of suboptimal phenotype to phenotypes of subsequent downstream functions. Mitigate when necessary

Table 3 only deals with individual propagations from two subsequent functions. In addition functional resonance can result from multiple aspects that are received in individual functions, from functional bypasses, redundant functional paths and other phenomena of functional resonance. This is especially important in the concluding steps in the FRAM methodology, being the aggregation of functional resonance and the management of performance variability. These principles will need to be studied by future research and can lead to updates of this guide. The steps 'aggregation of functional resonance and management of performance variability' are conceptually depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Steps 9-10 (out of a total of 10) from the FRAM-IA Framework.

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APPENDIX A: Ten-step FRAM-IA Framework Summary

The Figure from Appendix A represents a workflow with all the steps that are required concerning the application of the FRAM-IA framework. Appendix A is created to support the reader in maintaining oversight of the different aspects of the framework. The workflow includes the steps, required by traditional FRAM methodology, already known to experienced FRAM users. Novel steps for the IA extension, introduced in this guide are additionally marked with a ‘ * ’ symbol. The ‘ ** ’ symbol represents steps that are already part for the additional FRAM methodology, but nevertheless require a specific interpretation concerning the IA extension. It is recommended to regularly consult the appendix workflow (steps) while reading the different sections of this guide.

- 1. Describe functions in socio-technical activity - Section 2.1.1 – 2.1.2
 - 2. Determine aspects for couplings (in practice performed in parallel with step 3) - Section 2.1.3
 - 3. Connect aspects by couplings - Section 2.1.4
 - 4. Determine function/agent granularity and agent grouping for AI extension*- Section 2.1.7 – 3.2 (Function Granularity); Section 2.1.7 – 3.3 (Agent Granularity)
 - 5. Add dependency assessment – Section 3.4
 - 6. Add OPD Labels– Section 3.5
 - 7. Add JCS agents - Section 3.6
- Note that the FMV automatically assigns back-and-foreground functions (Section 2.1.5) by using grey and white respectively, but also that this information about back-and-foreground functions is lost when self-assigning colours. (See models before and after step 7). The identification of back-and-foreground functions is not central to the IA analysis and can still easily be derived without the FMV support. Using the colours for JCS agents on the other hand is supportive for an IA analysis and JCS perspective.
- 8. Update with actual/observed variability)** - Section 3.7 (if no observation, continue with potential variability only. Note that the only change in comparison to step 7 in the example from Appendix B Figure below is that the upstream dependency from coupling 4 has changed from green (step 7) to red (step 8), because of a hypothesised difference between potential variability (step 7 - green) and actual variability (step 8 - red).
 - 9. Assessing functional resonance (upstream-downstream propagation, broken links, and multiple-Input rules)** - Section 3.8 – 3.9 (Cf. FRAM stage #3). Propagation symbols have been added. Note that there are more symbols than used in step 9 of Appendix B Figure.
 - 10. Manage functional resonance by alternative functions, propagations, and improve dependencies** - Section 3.8 – 3.9 (Cf. FRAM stage #4). In the particular example of Appendix B Figure. an <new function> with |new couplings| has been created as an example to manage the negative propagation potential between functions C and D from previous step 9.

The accompanying Figure is displayed on the two next pages.

APPENDIX B: Resilience Analysis Matrix Representation of a FRAM Model with IA extension

The Figure from Appendix B presents another way of displaying the FRAM model with its traditional hexagon representation. The altered representation makes use of the Resilience Analysis Matrix (RAM) representation and has been subjected as part of the same PhD project for journal publications.

The accompanying figure is displayed on the next page. The interested reader can consult the publication below for more information on the RAM representation of the FRAM-IA framework.

Adriaensen, A., Berx, N., Pintelon, L., Costantino, F., Di Gravio, G., & Patriarca, R. (2022). Interdependence Analysis in Collaborative Robot Applications from a Joint Cognitive Functional Perspective. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 90(103320), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ergon.2022.103320>

Figure 13 (Annex B): Simple FRAM-IA model with RAM representation and legend, adapted from (Adriaensen et al. 2022).